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Leachate Characterisation and Assessment of Groundwater Quality: A Case of Soluos Dumpsite in Lagos State, Nigeria

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

Groundwater contamination due to municipal landfill sites is a threat to ground water integrity. This current research characterised the heavy metals in leachate from Soluos dumpsite in Lagos, Nigeria and assessed the groundwater quality at different distances from the dumpsite for both dry and wet seasons. The contaminants examined are lead, zinc, copper, nickel, chromium, iron, manganese, magnesium, calcium, sodium, potassium and chloride. The results showed that the concentration level of contaminants examined in groundwater samples in all the well investigated fall within the maximum acceptable concentration stipulated by World Health Organisation and National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control except for GW2 for wet season; but it will be higher than the level stipulated by the regulatory bodies in future based on the predicted values, hence there is a need to upgrade the dumpsite to prevent future contamination of groundwater. A predictive model for transport of contaminants through a porous medium used in this work predicted the contaminants concentration in groundwater samples near the dumpsite to a very appreciable level of above 93% confidence level, using finite difference method implemented in Matlab 7.0. This showed that the model parameters used which were obtained by sensitivity analysis of previous work of Jhamnani and Singh are suitable for Soluos dumpsite in Lagos State. Descriptive statistics such as mean, variation, standard deviation, standard error and coefficient of variance were used to describe the basic features of the results of groundwater samples.

Keywords: Leachate, contaminants, characterisation, groundwater, dumpsite.

INTRODUCTION

The consumption of available resources has resulted in municipal solid waste (MSW) from industrial to domestic activities, which affect human health. Improper management of solid waste areas has resulted in serious ecological, environmental and health problems. Such practices contribute to widespread environmental pollution as well as spread of diseases (Bakis and Tuncan, 2010). The intensity of man's activities has led to increasing volume of solid waste worldwide despite the current level of technological advancement and industrialization. Explosive population growth is one major factor responsible for increased municipal solid waste (Longe and Balogun, 2010). The precipitation that falls into a landfill, coupled with any disposed liquid waste, results in the extraction of water-soluble compounds and particulate matter of the waste and the subsequent formation of leachate (salami, 2012).

Once leachate is formed and is released to the groundwater environment, it will migrate downward through the unsaturated zone until it eventually reaches the saturated zone. Leachate then will follow the hydraulic gradient of the groundwater system and contaminate the groundwater. Threats to the groundwater from the unlined and uncontrolled landfills exist in many parts of the world, particularly in the under-developed and developing countries (Nigeria inclusive) where the hazardous industrial waste is also co-disposed with municipal waste and no provision to separate secured hazardous landfills exists (Kumar and Alappat, 2003). Even if there are no hazardous wastes placed in municipal landfills, the leachate is still reported as a significant threat to the groundwater (Lema et al., 1988; Lu, 1985). A number of incidences have been reported in the past where leachate had contaminated the surrounding soil and polluted the underlying groundwater aquifer or nearby surface water (Kumar et al., 2002; Kumar and Alappat, 2003; Masters, 1998; Lo, 1996; Chain and Dewalle, 1976; Kelly, 1976; Noble and Arnold, 1991; Qasim and Chiang, 1994; Reinhart and Grosh, 1998; Mc Bean, 1995).

The aims and objectives of this work are as follows:

- (i) to characterise leachate and assess the level of groundwater contamination due to leachate percolation from the unlined Soluos dumpsite in Alimosho Local Government area of Lagos State, Nigeria,
- (ii) develop suitable model parameters for Soluos dumpsite and

(iii) to validate a developed model with the field data from Soluos dumpsite. Inadequate solid waste management (SWM) is a major environmental problem in Lagos metropolis. There is an absence of any properly designed solid waste disposal facilities in the state therefore posing contamination risk to both groundwater and surface water (Longe and Balogun, 2010). Longe and Enekwechi (2007) described leachates outflow and infiltration as the most critical source of groundwater contamination from the existing solid waste management practices in Lagos State and thus constituted potential public health and environmental problem. Therefore this work is both timely and important, which justifies this work.

Study Area

The Soluos dumpsite is situated at Ikotun/Igando Local council development area of Alimosho Local Government in Lagos State, Nigeria. The dumpsite covers 3.2 hectares and surrounded by commercial, industrial and residential set up. It started operation in 1996. The dumpsite has witnessed rehabilitation which comprised reclamation of land, construction of accessible road for case of tipping, spreading and compaction of waste since inception (Longe and Balogun, 2010). The wastes are of different types, ranging from organic to inorganic, hazardous and non hazardous. Like in all other existing dumpsites in the state, the waste stream is made up of domestic, market, commercial, industrial and institutional origins (Longe and Balogun, 2010). The soluos dumpsite shown in plate 2.1 is a non-engineered landfill with a huge heap of waste. Trucks from different parts of Lagos State collect and bring wastes to this site and dump them in irregular fashion. The wastes are dumped without separation but the rag pickers who constitute the informal sector rummage through the waste, help in segregating them by collecting the plastic and metals and sell them to the recycling industries.

Plate2.1: A view of Soluos dumpsite in Alimosho Local Government of Lagos State, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Sampling of Leachate and Groundwater

The method of Bakis and Tuncan (2010) was used. Since the dumpsite was not equipped with a leachate collector, leachates were collected at the base of the dumpsite randomly from four different locations and were mixed prior to its analysis. The leachate samples were seasonally taken to determine the heavy metal concentrations in rainy and dry conditions. Leachate samples were collected using 1-litre plastic bottles that had been cleaned by soaking in 10% nitric acid and rinsed with distilled water, at the sampling site, the bottles were rinsed twice with the leachate to be sampled prior to filling and it was labeled LS.

In an effort to assess the groundwater quality, five sampling sites were selected within 500m from the dumpsite where samples were taken during rainy and dry season. Details of the sampling points are presented in Table 1. Groundwater samples were collected using 1 litre plastic bottles which had been cleaned by soaking in

10% nitric acid and rinsed with distilled water, at the sampling site as well, the bottles were rinsed three times with groundwater to be sampled prior to filling and the bottles were labeled GW1 to GW5.

Table 3.1: Site Specification for Samples.

Sample code	Sampling location	Distance from Landfill site(m)	Depth(m)
GW1	Commercial Centre	64	22
GW2	Block Industries	103	22
GW3	Religious Centre	194	22
GW4	Religious Centre	235	22
GW5	Residential Building	296	22
LS	Solid waste Site	-	22

Analytical Method

After sampling the leachate and groundwater, they were quickly transferred to the laboratory and stored in a cold room (4°C). The analysis was started without delay in the laboratory based on the priority to analyze parameters as prescribed by the Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Waste water (APHA, 1992). The analysis of heavy metal concentrations such as Fe, Cu, Pb, Cr, Cd, Ni, Zn, Mn, Na, K, Ca, Mg and Cl of the leachate and groundwater samples were determined using atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) for the two categories, which are rainy and dry season samples.

Contaminants Transport Model

The contaminant transport model equation (3.3.1) of Jhamanani and singh (2009) was solved using finite difference method implemented in Matlab 7.0 and was also validated by the field data from Soluos dumpsite in Lagos State, Nigeria, shown in Table 3.2.

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = \frac{D_h}{R_f} \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial z^2} - \frac{v}{R_f} \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \quad (3.3.1)$$

Where D_h = hydrodynamic dispersion coefficient, $D_h = D_e + D_{md}$

D_e = effective molecular diffusion, $D_e = \tau D_m$

τ = tortuosity of the medium, D_m = molecular diffusion coefficient

$\tau = \frac{1}{n^3}$, n = porosity of the medium

D_{md} =mechanical dispersion coefficient, $D_{md} = \alpha v$, α = dispersivity

v = advective velocity, R_f = retardation factor

Solving equation 3.3.1 yields:

$$C_T(0,t) = \frac{C_o - \frac{n}{H_f} v_z \sum_{t=0}^{t-1} C_T(0,t) \Delta t}{\left[1 + \frac{n}{H_f} v_z \Delta t \right]} \quad (3.3.2)$$

Where C_0 = initial concentration of contaminant at the source

C_T = concentration of contaminate at any time t

Table 3.3.1: Model parameters for simulation

S/N	Model Parameters	Unit	Value
1	Time	yr	50
2	Molecular diffusion coefficient	m ² /yr	0.027
3	Mechanical dispersion coefficient	m ² /yr	0.075
4	Effective molecular diffusion coefficient	m ² /yr	0.02
5	Dispersivity	M	0.15
6	Advective velocity	m/yr	0.5
7	Hydrodynamic dispersion	m ² /yr	0.095
8	Porosity		0.74
9	Retardation factor		1
10	Equivalent height of leachate	M	0.64
11	Δt	S	1
12	Δz	M	1.5

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4.1 and 4.2 show the contaminants concentrations in leachate and groundwater samples during dry and wet season respectively, while Table 4.3 shows the guideline on drinking water by World Health Organization and National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control. Tables 4.4 and 4.5 show the descriptive statistics characteristics of groundwater sample for dry and wet seasons respectively, while Table 4.6 and 4.7 show the experimental and simulated as well as percentage different values of contaminants for GW1 and GW5 respectively. Figures 4.1 to 4.12 and Figure 3.13 to 4.24 show the variation of contaminants concentrations with time at various depth for GW1 and GW5 respectively, during wet season.

Table 4.1: Characteristics of leachate from Soluos dumpsite and groundwater samples from nearby locations in dry season

S/N	Parameters (mg/l)	LS	GW1	GW2	GW3	GW4	GW5
1.	Pb	0.010	0.009	0.006	ND	0.001	0.004
2.	Cd	0.006	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
3.	Zn	0.861	0.461	0.986	0.424	0.594	0.281
4.	Cu	0.189	0.046	0.052	0.061	0.059	0.060
5.	Ni	0.196	0.028	0.036	0.019	0.020	0.016
6.	Cr	0.011	0.010	0.011	0.014	0.012	0.014
7.	Fe	0.156	0.110	0.121	0.116	0.122	0.134
8.	Mn	0.326	0.324	0.332	0.451	0.432	0.338
9.	Mg	1.067	1.020	1.004	1.022	0.671	0.771
10.	Ca	1.204	1.611	1.422	1.301	1.201	1.122
11.	Na	0.451	0.456	0.551	0.523	0.442	0.412
12.	K	0.310	0.330	0.312	0.351	0.304	0.256
13.	Cl	98	88	56	94	64	77

ND: Not detected

Table 4.2: Characteristics of leachate from Soluos dumpsite and groundwater samples from nearby locations in wet season

S/N	Parameters (mg/l)	LS	GW1	GW2	GW3	GW4	GW5
1.	Pb	0.005	0.011	0.009	0.04	ND	0.008
2.	Cd	0.002	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
3.	Zn	0.714	0.242	0.341	0.442	0.471	0.511
4.	Cu	0.176	0.041	0.045	0.052	0.072	0.061
5.	Ni	0.197	0.035	0.027	0.031	0.057	0.062
6.	Cr	0.010	0.009	0.011	0.014	0.017	0.015
7.	Fe	0.162	0.118	0.146	0.144	0.1201	0.186
8.	Mn	0.317	0.243	0.211	0.341	0.451	0.314
9.	Mg	0.781	1.106	1.328	1.314	0.451	0.314
10.	Ca	1.311	1.561	1.551	1.448	1.452	1.209
11.	Na	0.467	0.554	0.468	0.431	0.512	0.601
12.	K	0.325	0.418	0.511	0.426	0.412	0.318
13.	Cl	120	102	79	101	92	84

ND: Not detected

Table 4.3: Guideline on drinking water by World Health Organization (W.H.O) and National Agency for Food and Drug administration and Control (NAFDAC)

S/N	Parameters	Maximum Acceptable Concentration by W.H.O	Maximum Acceptable Concentration by NAFDAC
1.	Pb	0.01	0.01
2.	Cd	0.003	–
3.	Zn	5.0	5.0
4.	Cu	2.0	–
5.	Ni	–	–
6.	Cr	0.05	–
7.	Fe	0.05 – 0.30	–
8.	Mn	0.5	–
9.	Mg	50	30
10.	Ca	50	75
11.	Na	–	–
12.	K	1.0 – 2.0	10
13.	Cl	200	200

Source: NAFDAC (2011).

Table 4.4: Descriptive statistics for characteristics of groundwater sample in dry season

S/N	Parameters	Range	Mean	Variance	S.D	S.E	C.V
1.	Pb	0.005	0.004	7.6×10^{-6}	0.00276	0.00123	0.69
2.	Zn	0.705	0.549	0.0576	0.24	0.107	0.455
3.	Cu	0.015	0.055	3.3×10^{-5}	0.00575	0.00257	0.1034
4.	Ni	0.02	0.0242	5.3×10^{-5}	0.0072	0.00257	0.1034
5.	Cr	0.004	0.0122	2.56×10^{-6}	0.0016	0.00715	0.131
6.	Fe	0.024	0.121	6.32×10^{-5}	0.00795	0.003555	0.0657
7.	Mn	0.113	0.379	0.0026	0.0515	0.0103	0.136
8.	Mg	0.351	0.8976	0.0218	0.1477	0.066	0.1645
9.	Ca	0.489	1.3314	0.0296	0.1721	0.077	0.1293
10.	Na	0.139	0.478	0.00269	0.052	0.0232	0.109
11.	K	0.074	0.311	0.001	0.00317	0.00141	0.01
12.	Cl	38	75.80	202.56	14.23	6.364	0.188

Table 4.5: Descriptive statistics for characteristics of ground water sample in wet season

S/N	Parameters	Range	Mean	Variance	S.D	S.E	C.V
1.	Pb	0.003	0.013	0.000146	0.0121	0.0541	0.88971
2.	Zn	0.269	0.401	0.009468	0.0973	0.0435	0.2424
3.	Cu	0.031	0.054	1.25×10^{-6}	0.0011	5.02×10^{-4}	0.0207
4.	Ni	0.033	0.042	1.93×10^{-4}	0.0139	0.00623	0.3312
5.	Cr	0.008	0.0132	4.667×10^{-6}	0.0021	9.66×10^{-4}	0.1636
6.	Fe	0.083	0.159	9.136×10^{-4}	0.0302	0.0135	0.190
7.	Mn	0.24	0.312	7.0256×10^{-3}	0.0838	0.00314	0.2686
8.	Mg	0.158	1.1424	2.456×10^{-2}	0.1567	0.07	1.10
9.	Ca	0.352	1.4442	1.5663×10^{-2}	0.1251	0.055971	0.8662
10.	Na	0.236	0.4566	6.5148×10^{-3}	0.0807	0.0361	0.0589
11.	K	0.193	0.417	3.7488×10^{-3}	0.0612	0.02738	0.1468
12.	Cl	23	91.60	82.64	9.0906	4.06558	0.0992

Table 4.6: Experimental and simulated as well as percentage different values of contaminants for GW1

S/N	Contaminants	Experimental Values	Simulated values	Percentage difference
1.	Pb	0.011	0.01028	6.55
2.	Zn	0.242	0.2262	6.53
3.	Cu	0.041	0.03832	6.54
4.	Ni	0.035	0.03271	6.54
5.	Cr	0.009	0.008412	6.53
6.	Fe	0.118	0.1108	6.10
7.	Mn	0.243	0.2271	6.54
8.	Mg	1.106	1.034	6.51
9.	Ca	1.561	1.459	6.53
10.	Na	0.554	0.5178	6.53
11.	K	0.418	0.3907	6.53
12.	Cl	102	95.34	6.53

Table4.7: Experimental and simulated as well as percentage difference values of contaminants for GW5

S/N	Contaminants	Experimental Values	Simulated values	Percentage difference
1.	Pb	0.008	0.0075	6.25
2.	Zn	0.511	0.4776	6.54
3.	Cu	0.061	0.05702	6.52
4.	Ni	0.062	0.05795	6.53
5.	Cr	0.015	0.01402	6.53
6.	Fe	0.186	0.1739	6.50
7.	Mn	0.314	0.2935	6.53
8.	Mg	0.314	0.2935	6.53
9.	Ca	1.209	1.130	6.53
10.	Na	0.601	0.5618	6.52
11.	K	0.318	0.2972	6.54
12.	Cl	84	78.51	6.53

Fig.4.1: Variation of lead concentration with time for GW1.

Fig.4.2: Variation of zinc concentration with time for GW1.

Fig.4.3: variation of copper concentration with time for GW1.

Fig.4.4: variation of nickel concentration with time for GW1.

Fig.4.5: Variation of chromium concentration with time for GW1.

Fig.4.6: Variation of iron concentration with time for GW1.

Fig.4.7: Variation of manganese concentration with time for GW1.

Fig.4.8: Variation of magnesium with time for GW1.

Fig.4.9: Variation of calcium concentration with time for GW1.

Fig.4.10: Variation of sodium concentration with time for GW1.

Fig.4.11: Variation of potassium concentration with time for GW1.

Fig.4.12: Variation of chloride concentration with time for GW1.

Fig.4.13: Variation of lead concentration with time for GW5.

Fig.4.14: Variation of zinc concentration with time for GW5.

Fig.4.15: variation of copper concentration with time for GW5.

Fig.4.16: Variation of nickel concentration against time for GW5.

Fig.4.17: Variation of chromium concentration against time for GW5.

Fig.4.18: Variation of iron concentration against time for GW5.

Fig.4.19: Variation of manganese concentration with time for GW5.

Fig.4.20: Variation of magnesium concentration with time for GW5.

Fig.4.21: Variation of calcium concentration with time for GW5.

Fig.4.22: Variation of sodium concentration with time for GW5.

Fig.4.23: Variation of potassium concentration with time for GW5.

Fig.4.24:Variation of chloride concentration with time for GW5.

The contaminant concentrations are expected to decrease as distance increases from the dumpsite (Jhamnani and Singh, 2009) but there is a deviation in this work. From table 4.1.1, the contaminants concentration level of lead and magnesium decreases as the distance from the dumpsite increases. Other contaminants examined varied from the trend of lead and magnesium. In GW1 which is the closest to the dumpsite, the contaminants concentration of sodium and potassium are higher than that of leachate sample. In GW2, the contaminants concentration level of zinc, copper, Iron, manganese, sodium and potassium are higher than the level in GW1 and leachate sample except for nickel and manganese which the contaminant level is less than the level in leachate sample.

In GW3, the contaminant concentration level of copper, chromium, Iron, manganese, sodium, potassium and chloride are higher than the level in GW1, GW2 as well as the leachate sample. In GW4, the contaminant concentration of chromium and manganese are higher than the level in the leachate sample. In GW5, the contaminant concentration level of chromium and Iron are the highest among all the groundwater samples. The result of Table 4.1.1 has no definite pattern which is an indication that there is a secondary source of contaminants within the vicinity of the study area.

In Table 4.1.2, none of the contaminants follow the expected trend of decreasing contaminant concentration level as the distance from the dumpsite increases. In GW1, the concentration level of magnesium, calcium, sodium and potassium are higher than the concentration level in leachate sample. In GW2, the concentration level of zinc, copper, chromium, magnesium and potassium are higher than the level in GW1 and leachate sample. In GW3, the concentration level of zinc, copper, chromium, manganese are higher than the level in GW2 and GW1 with the exception of magnesium. In GW4, lead and cadmium were not detected. The concentration level of zinc, nickel and sodium are higher than that of GW3.

Moreover, the value of chromium, manganese, magnesium, calcium which are 0.017, 0.451, 0.451, and 0.452mg/l respectively in GW3 happens to be the highest among all groundwater samples. In GW5 cadmium was not detected, which is the same for all the groundwater samples. The concentration levels of zinc, nickel, chromium, Iron, and sodium in GW5 have the highest values among all the groundwater samples. The values are 0.511, 0.062, 0.015, 0.186 and 0.601mg/l respectively. These values are above the values in leachate sample. The results in Table 4.1.2 has no particular trend which is also the case in the result of Table 4.1.1 and this further buttress the likely presence of secondary source of contaminants in the vicinity of the study area.

From Figures 4.1.1 to 4.1.24, it can be seen that the variation of contaminants concentration show behaviour typical of a convectional landfill system. Simulated contaminants concentration in groundwater below the dumpsite facilities increases, reaches a peak and then declines. It was observed that as the depth increases

downward, the level of contaminants concentration decreases, that is the level of contaminants concentration is inversely proportional to the depth.

Though the level of contaminants measured in groundwater samples for both dry and wet season fall within the guideline of National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control and World Health Organisation for drinking water, it was obvious from Figures 4.1.1 to 4.1.24 that the concentrations of contaminants in the groundwater around the vicinity of the study area will increase above the level stipulated by the regulatory bodies therefore, there is a need to upgrade the dumpsite.

The soil stratigraphy of Lagos metropolis or the existing sequence of soil type occurring in the metropolis makes land-filling operation very risky, especially when one considers the prevalent high water table in Lagos (Longe and Balogun, 2010). However, the stratigraphy at Soluos dumpsite consisting of clay and silty clay appears to have significantly influenced the moderate level of contaminant found in groundwater samples.

The contaminants concentrations for wet season are higher than the contaminants concentrations for dry season which is due to the fact that during wet season, the volume of water available in landfill site for leaching solute from wastes is more than the dry season period. On this basis, the contaminants concentration of wet season were used for simulation of model equation 3.4.1 to predict the level of contaminants in groundwater using finite difference method implemented in Matlab 7.0. The model predicted the experimental results to a very high level of above 93% confidence level as shown in Table 4.1.6 and Table 4.1.7. This revealed that the model parameters of Table 3.4.1 used in this work, which were obtained through sensitivity analysis of the model parameters of Jhamnani and Singh are suitable for Soluos dump site.

Descriptive statistics which provides qualitative measure of accuracy about the contaminants such as mean, variance, standard deviation, standard error and coefficient of variance were used to describe the basic features of the field data obtained. In dry season, the mean, variance and standard deviation of contaminants except for chloride range from 0.004 to 1.3314, 2.56×10^{-6} to 0.0576 and 2.76×10^{-3} to 0.24 respectively, while the standard error and coefficient of variance of contaminants except for chloride range from 1.23×10^{-3} to 6.364 and 0.188 to 0.69 respectively. More so, in wet season, the mean, variance and standard deviation of contaminants except for chloride range from 0.0136 to 1.44442, 1.25×10^{-6} to 2.456×10^{-2} and 0.00216 to 0.1251 respectively, while standard error and coefficient of variance of contaminants except for chloride range from 5.02×10^{-4} to 0.0541 and 0.0207 to 0.8897 respectively.

CONCLUSION

The contaminants concentration is expected to decrease as the distance from the dumpsite increases but the experimental results of this work deviate from such a pattern. The contaminants concentration in groundwater samples in all the well investigated fall within the guideline of maximum acceptable concentration for drinking water by World Health Organization and National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control. It was cleared from the predicted results that the level of contaminants concentration in the groundwater in the vicinity of the study area will be above the level stipulated by the regulatory bodies in future. Hence there is a need to upgrading the dumpsite to prevent future contamination of groundwater.

The predictive transport model used in this work predicted the experimental results to a very appreciable level of more than 93% confidence level, hence the model parameters used in this work which were obtained through sensitivity analysis of model parameters of Jhamnani and Singh are suitable for Soluos dumpsite. Descriptive statistics which provides qualitative measure of accuracy about the samples such as mean, variance, standard deviation, standard error and coefficient of variance were used to describe the basic features of the experimental results.

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